

Single step determination of platinum(IV) in alloys, catalysts, complexes, environmental and pharmaceutical samples using *p*-[*N,N*-bis(2-chloroethyl)amino]benzaldehyde thiosemicarbazone

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Abstract : *p*-[*N,N*-Bis(2-chloroethyl)amino]benzaldehyde thiosemicarbazone is proposed as an analytical reagent for the spectrophotometric determination of platinum(IV). The reagent forms yellow colored complex with platinum(IV) in the concentration range of 0.016–0.080 *M* hydrochloric acid medium. Beer's law is obeyed in the concentration range up to 12.48 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-3}$. The optimum concentration range for minimum photometric error as determined by Ringbom's plot method is 3.12–10.92 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-3}$. The yellowish Pt^{IV}-reagent complex shows a maximum absorbance at 390 nm, with molar absorptivity of $2.05 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and Sandell's sensitivity of the complex from Beer's data, for $D = 0.001$, is 0.012 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$. The composition of the Pt^{IV}-CEABT complex is found to be 1 : 2 (M : L) by Job's method and by mole-ratio method. The relative error and coefficient of variation ($n = 6$) of the method does not exceed $\pm 0.80\%$ and $\pm 0.32\%$ respectively. The interference of various cations and anions in the method were studied. The proposed method was successfully used for the determination of Pt^{IV} in alloys, catalysts, complexes, environmental and pharmaceutical samples. The method is rapid as the Pt^{IV}-CEABT complex is soluble in water-ethanol-DMF medium and not requiring any time consuming extraction method for the complex.

Keywords : Spectrophotometric determination, Pt^{IV} determination, chromogenic reagent, *p*-[*N,N*-bis(2-chloroethyl)amino]benzaldehyde thiosemicarbazone, CEABT.

Introduction

Platinum is a rare, scarce and costly metal and it shows certain properties which make it unique. The specific chemical and physical properties of this metal are of essential use for many different applications. Platinum is known as the environmental metal. As a matter of fact, approximately 20% of the goods manufactured in the world contain platinum or are produced using platinum. Platinum-group metals are widely used as catalysts in many chemical processes¹. A platinum-based catalyst removed 90% of the carbon monoxide, unburned hydrocarbons and nitrogen oxides in exhaust gas from vehicles. Platinum-based catalysts are very effective, e.g. in ammonia oxidation, petroleum reforming, pharmaceutical industry, and fuel cells. Platinum-containing compounds have

found important application in treatment of cancerous tumors and rheumatoid arthritis. The most active complexes of platinum were found to be *cis* isomers of dichlorodiammine-platinum(II), Pt(NH₃)₂Cl₂ and tetrachlorodiammine-platinum(IV), Pt(NH₃)₂Cl₄. *Trans*-complexes were found to be inactive and are toxic but do not have antitumor properties². A study of platinum levels in the diet was conducted in 1986 on market-basket samples in Sydney, Australia³. The major pathway of platinum into the human body at the population level is via the diet, with an average dietary intake of 1.44 $\mu\text{g/day}$. The toxicological effects of platinum in humans are confined to certain of its complex halides, salts, and to the antitumor agents, *cis*-platin of its analogs. The platinum group compounds like chloroplatinate is not highly

toxic but may cause allergic reactions to human beings. Owing to its corrosion-resistant nature and alloying ability, platinum and its alloys are used in dental and medicinal devices and in manufacturing jewelry⁴. Considering these excellent and extensive applications of platinum and the toxic nature of its compounds, there is always a need for monitoring the level of platinum in various samples. Several analytical techniques have been reported for the determination of platinum in various samples using Inductively coupled plasma (ICP), Atomic emission spectrophotometry, Mass spectroscopy, Atomic absorption spectrometry, Graphite furnace atomic absorption spectrometry, Neutron activation analysis and Capillary electrophoresis which are very expensive compared to spectrophotometric method, this method have gained popularity as an analytical tool for platinum determination of such samples in respect of simplicity and low operating costs. A search in the literature also reveals that only a limited number of thiosemicarbazones have been reported for the spectrophotometric determination of platinum. This is in contrast to copper and palladium, for which a large number of thiosemicarbazones have been suggested as reagents. A brief account of these methods is given in previously reported paper⁵.

Present work :

In the present work, *p*-[*N,N*-bis(2-chloroethyl)-amino]benzaldehyde thiosemicarbazone (CEABT) is proposed as a chromogenic reagent for the trace determination of platinum(IV). The color reaction between platinum and CEABT, the optimum conditions for its determination, composition of the complex, molar absorptivity, sensitivity, selectivity of the method, and effect of diverse ions on the accuracy of the method have been studied. The applications of the proposed method for the determination of platinum in alloys, catalysts, complexes, and environmental and pharmaceutical samples have also been explored.

Materials and methods :

Apparatus and reagents :

A Shimadzu (Model - 160A) double beam UV/Vis spectrophotometer with 1.0 cm quartz cell and ELICO pH meter (LI 127) with combined electrode is used for the measurements of absorbance and pH respectively. Infrared spectra were recorded in Thermo-FTIR in the

range of 4000–400 cm^{-1} . All reagents, chemicals, platinum alloys, catalyst and pharmaceutical samples are readily available in Sigma-Aldrich (India), used were of analytical or chemically pure grade without any further purification. Water sample are collected from Chennai (Tamilnadu). The starting material *p*-[*N,N*-bis(2-chloroethyl)amino]benzaldehyde thiosemicarbazone was prepared as per the reported procedure⁶.

Stock solution of platinum chloride solution :

The stock solution platinum(IV) chloride was prepared by dissolving 1 g of chloroplatinic acid ($\text{H}_2\text{PtCl}_6 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$) in water and the solution was made up to 500 mL using doubly distilled water. The solution was standardized gravimetrically by the formic acid method⁷ and spectrophotometrically by using piperonal thiosemicarbazone⁸. This stock solution was further diluted to get $3.12 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ with double distilled water.

CEABT solution (0.013%) :

This solution was prepared by dissolving the requisite amount of *p*-[*N,N*-bis(2-chloroethyl)amino]benzaldehyde thiosemicarbazone in a known volume of pure acetone.

Solutions of foreign ions :

The stock solution of various metal ions and anions were prepared by dissolving the appropriate metal salts in distilled water or with suitable dilute acids and making up to a known volume.

Procedure :

An aliquot of the solution, containing 78–273 μg of Pt^{IV} was pipetted out into a 25 mL standard flask. 5 mL of 0.3 *M* HCl, 2–3 mL of CEABT (*M* : *L* : 1 : 2), 5 mL dimethylformamide, 5 mL of ethanol were added and the mixture was diluted up to the mark with double distilled water. After 5 min the absorbance was measured at 390 nm against a reagent blank. The platinum content in the unknown sample was determined using a concurrently prepared calibration graph.

Analysis of platinum alloys :

A known weight of the alloy sample was carefully dissolved in aqua-regia, evaporated to near dryness and cooled to room temperature. The residue was dissolved in double distilled water and made up to a known volume. The stock solution was standardized gravimetrically by the formic acid method⁷ and spectrophotometrically

by using piperonal thiosemicarbazone⁸. Aliquots of this solution were used for the estimation of platinum as per the proposed procedure.

Analysis of platinum complexes :

Platinum complexes with thiosemicarbazide and 4-amino-3,5-dimercapto-1,2,4-triazole were prepared and purified as per the reported procedure^{9,10}. A known weight of the complex was carefully decomposed with minimum amount of aqua-regia and evaporated to near dryness. Then the residue was dissolved in minimum amount of distilled water and filtered. The filtrate was made up to a known volume with double distilled water. Then the stock solution was standardized gravimetrically⁷ by formic acid method and spectrophotometrically by using piperonal thiosemicarbazone⁸. Aliquots of the solution were used for the estimation of platinum as per the proposed procedure.

Analysis of platinum catalysts :

A known weight of the catalyst was digested with aqua-regia and evaporated to near dryness. The residue was dissolved in distilled water and filtered. The filtrate was made up to a known volume with double distilled water. The stock solution was standardized gravimetrically by the formic acid method⁷ and spectrophotometrically by the piperonal thiosemicarbazone method⁸. Suitable aliquots of this solution were used for the estimation of platinum as per the proposed procedure.

Determination of platinum in pharmaceutical samples :

Solution from cisplatin injection containing 10 mg/ml cisplatin and carboplatin containing 10 mg/ml carboplatin were added to aqua-regia (5 ml) and was heated to near dryness. The process was repeated for two to three times, and then residue was dissolved in water and made up to 25 ml with double-distilled water. The stock solution was standardized spectrophotometrically by the piperonal thiosemicarbazone method⁸. Suitable volumes of these solutions were taken and analyzed as per the proposed procedure.

Determination of platinum in environmental water samples :

Water samples were collected in polythene bottles from tap water, river water, and spring water taken from different locations of Tamilnadu particularly in Chennai. After collection nitric acid (1 mL) was added as a preser-

vative and filtered (with Whatman filter paper No. 40). Each filtered environmental water sample (1000 mL) was evaporated nearly to dryness with a mixture of 2 mL of conc. H₂SO₄ and 5 mL of conc. HNO₃. After cooling, addition of 5 mL of conc. HNO₃ were repeated and heating to dense white fumes continue or until the solution becomes colorless. The solution was then cooled and neutralized with dil. NH₄OH in the presence of 1 to 2 mL of a 0.01% (w/v) tartrate solution. The resulting solution was then filtered and quantitatively transferred into 100 mL standard flask and make up to the mark with distilled water. The stock solution was standardized spectrophotometrically by the piperonal thiosemicarbazone method⁸. Suitable volumes of these solutions were taken and analyzed as per the proposed procedure.

Results and discussion

Absorption spectra :

The reagent forms a sparingly soluble yellow complex with Pt^{IV} in aqueous medium. The complex was found to be soluble in the aqueous solution containing 20% (v/v) DMF and 20% (v/v) ethanol. The absorption spectrum of the Pt^{IV}-CEABT complex was recorded against the reagent blank. Similarly, the absorption spectrum of the reagent was recorded against the solvent as blank. The absorption spectra of both the reagent and the complex are shown in Fig. 1. The spectra shows that the Pt^{IV}-CEABT complex and the reagent have maximum

Fig. 1. (A) Absorption spectra of Pt-CEABT complex vs CEABT blank, Pt^{IV} = 6.24 µg mL⁻¹. (B) Absorption spectra of CEABT vs acetone blank, [CEABT] = 6.24 µg mL⁻¹.

absorbance at 390 nm and 350 nm, respectively. The reagent has a negligibly small absorbance at the λ_{\max} of the complex. Thus, further absorbance measurements of the complex were made at 390 nm.

Composition of the complex :

The composition of the Pt^{IV}-CEABT complex was studied by Job's method of continuous variation¹¹ and also by the mole ratio method¹². In these methods, equimolar solutions of Pt^{IV} and CEABT were used. The results are presented in Figs. 2 and 3. The continuous variation method shows a maximum at the mole fraction of plati-

Fig. 2. Continuous variation plot. Pt^{IV} = [CEABT] = $3.998 \times 10^{-4} M$.

Fig. 3. Mole-ratio plot. Pt^{IV} = [CEABT] = $7.998 \times 10^{-4} M$, Volume of Pt^{IV} solution taken = 1 mL.

num 0.333, indicating the formation of a 1 : 2 complex (Pt : R). Further support to this, comes from the results of mole-ratio method.

Effect of the medium :

The reagent forms a sparingly soluble yellow complex with Pt^{IV} in aqueous medium and the complex was found to be completely soluble in aqueous DMF-ethanol medium, containing 20% (v/v) DMF and 20% (v/v) ethanol. A preliminary investigation of the pH studies using different buffers shows that the complex has a maximum absorbance in acid medium. Further attempts were made to investigate the effect of different acids such as HCl, H₂SO₄, HNO₃ and CH₃COOH on the absorbance of the complex. These studies revealed that the maximum absorbance of the complex was in the hydrochloric acid medium. In order to find out the optimum concentration of hydrochloric acid for complete color development, absorbance measurements were carried out at different concentrations of hydrochloric acid. The results are presented in the form of a plot of absorbance versus molarity of HCl (Fig. 4). It is clear from the plot that the absorbance of the complex is maximum and constant in the concentration range of 0.016–0.080 M of HCl.

Fig. 4. Effect of concentration of HCl on absorbance. Pt^{IV} = $6.24 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$.

Rate of reaction and stability of color :

The experiments were carried out with a sample solution containing a constant amount of platinum and measuring its absorbance at regular interval of time. The results are presented as a plot of absorbance versus time

(Fig. 5). These results show that the color reaction between Pt^{IV} and CEABT is fast and color development takes place soon after the mixing of the reagents. However, the reaction mixture was allowed to stand for five minutes before measuring its absorbance to ensure the maximum color development. It is also seen from the graph that the color of the solution remains stable for about 120 min.

Fig. 5. Color stability of Pt^{IV} -CEABT complex. $\text{Pt}^{\text{IV}} = 6.24 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$.

Effect of reagent concentration :

The effect of reagent concentration on the color development was studied by measuring the absorbance of the solutions containing varying concentrations of the reagent with a fixed amount of Pt^{IV} . The results are presented as a plot of absorbance against concentration of the reagent (Fig. 6). It is evident from the graph that 2 moles of CEABT per mole of Pt^{IV} are required for maximum color development. Further more, 10 fold excess of the reagent over the quantity of the reagent required does not show any substantial change in the absorbance.

Order of addition of reagents :

Experiments were carried out with a fixed amount of Pt^{IV} and changing the order of addition of the reagents. The results are presented in Table 1. The results indicate that the order of the addition of reagent does not have any effect on the absorbance of the complex.

Effect of temperature :

The effect of temperature on the maximum color de-

Fig. 6. Effect of reagent concentration on absorbance of Pt^{IV} -CEABT complex. $\text{Pt}^{\text{IV}} = 7.998 \times 10^{-4} M$; $[\text{CEABT}] = 16 \times 10^{-4} M$; volume of Pt^{IV} taken = 1 mL.

velopment was studied by performing the color reactions at different temperature and measuring absorbance as per the procedures. These results show that there is no appreciable change in the absorbance values of both the complexes up to 50°C . But at higher temperature, the absorbance value tends to decrease gradually. In the present work, the color reaction is carried out at laboratory temperature ($27\text{--}30^\circ\text{C}$).

Beer's law and optimum concentration range :

In order to determine the concentration range in which Beer's law is valid, absorbance values of Pt^{IV} -CEABT complex were measured under optimum conditions at various concentrations of Pt^{IV} in the solution. The results are presented in the form of a plot of absorbance versus molar concentration of Pt^{IV} (Fig. 7). It is seen from the graph that, Beer's law is obeyed up to $12.48 \mu\text{g}$ of Pt^{IV} . The optimum concentration range for maximum precision was determined by Ringbom's plot method¹³. The percentage transmittance of the complex solutions were plotted versus log of Pt^{IV} concentration (Fig. 8). The linear portion of the plot suggests that platinum(IV) can be precisely determined in the concentration range $3.12\text{--}10.92 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$.

Molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity :

The molar absorptivity¹⁴ of the Pt^{IV} -CEABT complex was calculated to be $2.05 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The Sandell's sensitivity of the method is $0.0122 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ at 390 nm .

Table 1. Effect of order of addition of reagents

Order of addition of reagents ^a	Absorbance at 390 nm
Pt ^{IV} + 0.3 M HCl + 0.013% CEABT + DMF + ethanol + water	0.523
Pt ^{IV} + 0.013% CEABT + 0.3 M HCl + DMF + ethanol + water	0.521
Pt ^{IV} + 0.013% CEABT + DMF + ethanol + 0.3 M HCl + water	0.521
Pt ^{IV} + 0.3 M HCl + DMF + ethanol + 0.013% CEABT + water	0.523
Pt ^{IV} + DMF + ethanol + 0.013% CEABT + water + 0.3 M HCl	0.523

^aAverage of four determination.

Fig. 7. Beer's law plot of Pt^{IV}-CEABT complex. Pt^{IV} = 1-12.48 µg mL⁻¹.

Fig. 8. Ringbom plot of complex. Pt^{IV}-CEABT, Pt^{IV} = 3.12-10.92 µg mL⁻¹.

Precision and accuracy of the method :

To assess the precision and accuracy of the method, determinations were carried out for a set of six measure-

ment of 3.12-10.92 µg mL⁻¹ of Pt^{IV} in water, under the optimized experimental condition. The results are presented in the Table 2. These results reveal that the relative error, standard deviation and coefficient of variation do not exceed ±0.80%, 0.011 and 0.32% respectively. From these result it is reasonable to infer that the proposed method is precise and accurate.

Table 2. Precision and accuracy in the determination of Pt^{IV}

Pt ^{IV} (µg mL ⁻¹)		Relative error (%)	Standard deviation	Coefficient of variation (%)
Taken	Found ^a			
3.12	3.11	-0.32	0.010	0.32
4.68	4.67	-0.21	0.008	0.19
6.24	6.23	-0.16	0.007	0.11
7.80	7.79	-0.13	0.011	0.14
9.36	9.35	-0.11	0.011	0.12

^aAverage of six determination (n = 6).

Effect of foreign ions :

The influence of the presence of diverse ions on the absorbance value of Pt^{IV}-CEABT complex system was studied with 6.24 µg mL⁻¹ Pt^{IV} in the presence of foreign ions. An error of ±2% in the absorbance value was considered as the tolerance limit. The results are presented in Table 3. No interference was observed for the following ions at the amounts in µg mL⁻¹ shown : Pb^{II} (800), Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Mn (4000), Co^{II} (300), Ni^{II} (46), Fe^{II} (2), Mg^{II} and Hg^{II} (1), Ba^{II} (50), La^{III}, Y^{III}, Ce^{III}, Zr^{III} and Al^{III} (400), Ru^{III} (5), Rh (40), Cr^{III} and Tl^{III} (2), Se^{IV} (50), Sn^{IV} (50), U^{VI} (400), chloride (4000), fluoride (2000), sulfate (500), bromide and acetate (400), citrate, tartarate(15). However, the presence of Cu^{II}, Pd^{II} and iodide cause severe interference. The interference of Pd^{II} and Cu^{II} is attributed to the formation of their respective colored complexes and hence cause higher absorbance. The presence of iodide decreases the intensity of color. Tolerance of Fe^{II} up to 20 µg mL⁻¹ can be achieved by adding 200 µg of NaF.

Table 3. Tolerance limit of diverse ions in the determination of 6.24 mg mL⁻¹ Pt^{IV}

Ion added	Tolerance limit (µg mL ⁻¹)	Ion added	Tolerance limit (µg mL ⁻¹)
Ba ^{II}	70	Se ^{IV} and Sn ^{IV}	60
Ca ^{II}	50	U ^{VI}	350
Mg ^{II}	30	Mo ^{VI}	30
Zn ^{II}	4000	Fluoride	2000
Pb ^{II}	750	Chloride	4000
Cd ^{II} and Mn ^{II}	4000	Bromide	400
Co ^{II}	400	Acetate	30
Ni ^{II}	40	Sulphate	500
Fe ^{II}	2	Nitrate	500
Fe ^{II} *	20		
Hg ^{II}	30	Phosphate	75
La ^{III} , Y ^{III} , Ce ^{III} , Zr ^{III} and Al ^{III}	400	Thiocyanate	15
Ru ^{III}	5	Borate	200
Rh ^{III}	45	Thiosulphate	60
Tl ^{III} and Cr ^{III}	2	EDTA	2

Application of the method :

The utility of the proposed method was studied by analyzing samples of platinum alloys, catalyst, complexes, environmental and pharmaceutical samples. The results are presented in Tables 4–9. The result shows that the platinum content in the above samples can be estimated by the proposed method with a fair degree of accuracy.

Table 4. Determination of platinum in alloys (*n* = 5)

Platinum alloys	Platinum taken (µg mL ⁻¹)	Platinum found (µg mL ⁻¹)	Relative error (%)
Pt-Ru (95.2–4.8%)	6.20	6.18	-0.32
Pt-Ir (80–20%)	6.50	6.49	-0.15

Table 5. Determination of platinum in complexes (*n* = 5)

Complex	Pt ^{IV} calculated (%)	Pt ^{IV} found (%)	Relative error (%)
Pt(CH ₃ N ₃ S) ₂ Cl ₂ ^a	43.53	43.18	-0.80
Pt(C ₂ H ₂ N ₄ S ₂) ₂ ^b	40.02	39.82	-0.49

^aPlatinum complex of thiosemicarbazide. ^bPlatinum complex of 4-amino-3,5-dimercapto-1,2,4-triazole.

Table 6. Determination of platinum in catalyst (*n* = 5)

Platinum catalyst	Platinum (Certified value) (%)	Platinum found (%)	Relative error (%)
Pt-Al ₂ O ₃ catalyst	5	4.97	-0.60
Pt-Charcoal catalyst	5	4.98	-0.40

Table 7. Determination of platinum in pharmaceutical samples (*n* = 5)

Sample	Amount Pt ^{IV} present		Relative error (%)
	Certi. value (mg)	Present method	
Platosin (cisplatin) injection	10.00	9.94	-0.60
Carboplatin injection	10.00	9.96	-0.40

Table 8. Determination of platinum in environmental water samples

Sample	Platinum (µg mL ⁻¹) ^a		Relative error (%)	Recovery (%)
	Added	Found ^a		
Distilled water	4.68	4.66	-0.42	99.57
	6.24	6.23	-0.16	99.83
River water	4.68	4.67	-0.21	99.78
	6.24	6.22	-0.32	99.67
Lake water	4.68	4.65	-0.64	99.35
	6.24	6.21	-0.48	99.51
Well water	4.68	4.65	-0.64	99.35
	6.24	6.21	-0.48	99.51

^aAverage of five determinations; ND - Non detectable.

Table 9. Determination of platinum in synthetic mixtures of ions (*n* = 5)

Composition of mixtures (µg mL ⁻¹)	Found (µg mL ⁻¹)	Relative error (%)
Pt ^{IV} (6.24 µg mL ⁻¹) (A)	6.24	0.00
(A) + Ru ^{III} (0.5 µg mL ⁻¹)	6.24	0.00
(A) + Rh ^{III} (0.5 µg mL ⁻¹)	6.23	-0.16
(A) + Ir ^{III} (0.5 µg mL ⁻¹)	6.22	-0.32
(A) + Zn ^{II} (5 µg mL ⁻¹) + Pb(II) (1 µg mL ⁻¹)	6.21	-0.48
(A) + Ni ^{II} (1 µg mL ⁻¹) + Rh ^{III} (1 µg mL ⁻¹)	6.23	-0.16
(A) + Co ^{II} (1 µg mL ⁻¹) + Al ^{III} (0.2 µg mL ⁻¹)	6.21	-0.48
(A) + Mn ^{II} (0.5 µg mL ⁻¹) + Rh ^{III} (1 µg mL ⁻¹)	6.24	0.00

Conclusions :

The CEABT complex forms a 1 : 2 yellow complex with Pt^{IV}. Beer's law is valid up to 12.48 µg mL⁻¹ and optimum concentration range for the determination of platinum(IV) is 3.12–10.92 µg mL⁻¹. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity of the method are found to be 2.05 × 10⁴ dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ and 0.012 µg cm⁻² res-

pectively. The relative error and coefficient of variation ($n = 5$) for the method do not exceed $\pm 0.80\%$ and $\pm 0.32\%$ respectively. Since the method tolerates a number of metal ions commonly associated with platinum, it can be employed for the determination of platinum in alloys, catalysts, complexes, environmental and pharmaceutical samples. The method is rapid as the Pt^{IV} -CEABT complex is soluble in water-ethanol-DMF mixture and not requiring any time consuming extraction techniques for this complex.

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